

The Relationship of Family Harmony with Delinquency in Teenagers in SMAN 1 Terangun

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Abstract-This research is a quantitative correlational study that aims to determine the relationship of family harmony with juvenile delinquency in SMAN 1 Terangun. Subjects involved in the study were 59 teenagers taken by simple random sampling technique. Data collection uses two scales, namely the scale of family harmony and the scale of juvenile delinquency. The product-moment correlation calculation results show that there is a relationship between family harmony with juvenile delinquency in SMAN 1 Terangun which is shown from the correlation coefficient where $r_{xy} = -0,389$; $p = 0,002 < 0,050$. The empirical mean of family harmony variable is 55.22 <from the hypothetical mean of 72.5 which means relatively low and juvenile delinquency variable of 78.25> of the hypothetical mean of 65 which means relatively high. This means that the lower the level of family harmony, the higher the level of juvenile delinquency in SMAN 1 Terangun.

Keywords- Family harmony, juvenile delinquency.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teenagers are a transition between childhood and adulthood. At this time the child is experiencing a period of growth and development in his physical and psychological. This period is considered as a very important period in life, especially in forming one's personality, this period starts around the age of 12 years and ends at the age of 18 to 22 years (Dryfoos & Barkin in Santrock, 2007). Adolescence is a period of hurricanes (strum und Drang), which reflects the turbulent modern culture due to conflicting values (Sarwono, 2016). As a teenager who grows into adulthood, many changes occur in his personality, encouraging them to find and strengthen their true identity. The process of searching for identity becomes a very absolute thing to happen, at this stage adolescents will tend to do things that they think have never been done so that the curiosity of adolescents is higher which sometimes leads to deviant behaviour (Erikson in Santrock, 2002).

According to Sarwono (2016), deviant behaviour is also referred to as juvenile delinquency. Lately, the phenomenon of juvenile delinquency in society is increasing. Mischief is like a circle that never breaks, continued to connect from time to time increasingly complicated. Delinquency in adolescence appears as a reaction to the experience of social interaction of adolescents who fail and are not directed to obtain satisfaction with the need to be accepted and avoid rejection, lack of moral education and mental development of adolescents and various situations of violence that occur in many communities have a major influence on the emergence of behaviour delinquency in teenagers.

Juvenile delinquency is socially caused by neglect so that they develop a distorted form of behaviour. Santrock (2007)

states that juvenile delinquency is a range of behaviours ranging from unacceptable social behaviour to unlawful actions. Some research on delinquency conducted by students, researchers say that from year to year has increased. Based on data revealed by the National Narcotics Agency (BNN), cases of drug abuse continue to increase among adolescents. From 2.21% (4 million people) in 2015 to 2.8% (around 5 million people) in 2016. The next one is free sex. The third is student brawl which has recently increased compared to the previous year 2015.

Another form of juvenile delinquency is a large number of teenagers who often store pornographic images or videos on their cell phones. As happened in Surabaya. Educational hotline institutions based in East Java revealed that 90% of students in Surabaya store pornographic films or pictures on their cellphones. The result is 92% of female students have seen images and watched porn on their cell phones while for male students 97%. Based on the phenomena described above juvenile delinquency also occurs in SMA N 1 Terangun. In line with the results of the researchers' interviews with the school, said that in the school delinquency is increasing like brawls between friends at school, brawls that occur between village A with village B. In addition teens in high school also commit delinquency such as stealing, ditching during hours lessons take place, some smoke, fight teachers, have sex before marriage, and elope.

Many factors cause delinquency in adolescents, one of which is family factors (Jamaludin, 2016). Many studies conducted by experts find that adolescents who come from caring, warm, and harmonious families can adapt and socialize well with the surrounding environment and adolescents who have a good adjustment in school, usually have a family background harmonious (Santrock, 2007).

Based on the results of several studies found that one of the factors causing juvenile delinquency is the failure of parents as role models for children, besides, a family atmosphere that creates insecurity and unpleasant and bad family relationships can cause psychological dangers for every age especially in adolescence (Hawari in Hasanah, 2015). The causes of juvenile delinquency are caused because children do not get attention, affection and educational guidance of parents because fathers and mothers are busy taking care of their problems. Later they sought compensation for their inner concerns outside the family environment, which was to become a member of a criminal gang and then commit many criminal acts (Kartono, 2014).

In line with some of the results of the study above, the researcher is interested in further researching the relationship of family harmony with the delinquency of teenagers in SMA N 1 Terangun. Researchers chose this location because in the last year the juvenile delinquency in the high school was getting higher and wider

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Teenagers

The term teenagers or adolescence comes from the Latin word *adolescere* which means to grow or grow to adulthood, as well as people of antiquity, looked at puberty and adolescence is no different from other periods in life span, children are considered to be adults when they can hold reproduction. The term adolescence, as it is used today, has a broader meaning, including mental, emotional, social, and physical maturity (Hurlock, 2006)

According to Piaget (in Hurlock, 2006) psychologically adolescence is the age of an individual becoming integrated with adult society. The age of the child no longer feels below the level of the older people, but is at the same level, at least in matters of rights. Mappiare (in Ernawati S, 2002) states, that adolescence lasts between the ages of 12 years to 21 years for women and 13 years to 22 years for men. Hurlock (2006) mentions adolescence is characterized by several characteristics including:

1. Adolescence is considered an important period
2. Adolescence is considered a transitional period
3. Adolescence is a period of change
4. Adolescence as a problematic age
5. Adolescence is a period of searching for identity
6. Adolescence as an age that causes fear
7. Adolescence as an unrealistic age
8. Adolescence as the threshold of adulthood.

According to Erikson (in Santrock, 2007), the main task of adolescents is to face identity versus identity confusion. The task of this development aims to look for self-identity so that later adolescents can become unique adults with valuable roles in society.

The task of adolescent development described by Sarwono (2016), namely:

1. Accept his physical state and use his body effectively
2. Receive a more mature relationship with peers of each gender
3. Accept the role of the sexes of each type both male and female
4. Trying to break away from emotional dependence on parents and other adults
5. Prepare for an economic career
6. Preparing for marriage and family life
7. Plan responsible social behaviour
8. Achieve certain values and ethical systems as guidelines for behaviour

B. Juvenile Delinquency

Etymologically juvenile delinquency can be translated by a juvenile which means a child while delinquency means crime. Thus the etymological understanding is child crime. Juvenile

delinquency is adolescents who behave deviate from social norms, religion and harm their safety or violate Jensen's law (in Sarwono, 2016). The term juvenile delinquency refers to a broad range, from socially unacceptable behaviour to status violations to criminal acts (Kartono, 2006).

According to Jensen (in Sarwono, 2016), many factors cause juvenile delinquency. In general, several factors that cause juvenile delinquency include:

1. Individual factors and environmental factors
2. Cultural factors
3. Economic factors
4. Social factors
5. Labelling/labelled naughty
6. Gender factors.

Sarwono (2016) said there are four aspects of juvenile delinquency, including:

1. Behaviour that causes physical casualties to others Such as fighting, rape, robbery, murder and others.
2. Behaviour that results in material casualties Such as vandalism, theft, pickpocketing, extortion and others.
3. Social behaviour that does not cause casualties on the side of others Such as prostitution, drug abuse and sex before marriage.
4. Behaviour that is against the status Like denying a child as a student by truant, denying the status of parents by going away from home or by denying the words of parents.

C. Family Harmony

In terms of harmony comes from the word *harmonious* which means harmonious, harmonious. The emphasis of harmony is the state of harmony or harmony (Big Indonesian Dictionary, in Hasanah, 2015). While the family is the smallest social unit that provides a foundation for adolescent development, while the environment and schools contribute to the nuances of adolescent development, therefore good or bad the structure of the family and surrounding communities gives good or bad influence on the growth of adolescent personality (Kartono, 2014).

Harmonious or prosperous family is an important goal in the family. According to Gunarsa (2003), the factors forming the harmonious family include:

1. Attention, which is to put the heart on all family members as the main basis for a good relationship between family members. Both in family development by paying attention to events in the family, and looking for cause and effect problems, there are also changes in each of its members.
2. Knowledge. The need to increase knowledge without stopping to expand insight is needed in living family life. It is very necessary to know the family members, that is, every change in the family, and changes in family members.
3. Introduction of all family members. This means self-knowledge and good self-knowledge is important to foster understanding. When self-knowledge has been achieved, it will be easier to highlight all the events or events that occur in the family. The problem will be more easily overcome, because of the many backgrounds more quickly revealed and resolved.

4. Acceptance, which means with all the weaknesses, weaknesses, and strengths, he should still get a place in the family. This attitude will produce a positive atmosphere and the development of warmth that underlies the growth of potential and interests of family members.
5. Business improvement, namely by developing each of the aspects of his family optimally, this is tailored to each ability of each, the goal is to create changes and eliminate boredom.

Meanwhile, according to Harlock, (2002), factors that influence family harmony are interpersonal communication, family economic level, parental attitudes, and family size. According to Sarwono, (in Maniriyanto, 2014), a harmonious family or a happy family is when in life it has shown the factors of mental well-being, physical well-being, the balance between expenses and family income.

According to Hawari (in Hasanah, 2015), six aspects of family harmony are:

1. Creating religious life in the family

A harmonious family is marked by the creation of religious life in the house. This is important because in religion there are moral values and ethical life. Based on several studies, it is found that non-religious families with low commitment or no religious values tend to have conflicts and disputes within the family, with an atmosphere like this, the child will feel uncomfortable at home and most likely the child will look for another environment who can receive it.

2. Having time with family

A harmonious family always provides time to be with his family, whether it's just gathering, eating together, accompanying children to play and listen to problems and complaints of children, in this togetherness the child will feel himself needed and cared for by his parents, so that the child will feel at home in home.

3. Having good communication between family members

Communication is the basis for creating harmony in the family. As teenagers will feel safe if their parents look harmonious, because harmony will provide a sense of security and peace for children, good communication within the family will also be able to help teens to solve problems they face outside the home, in this case in addition to acting as parents, mother and father also have to act as friends, so that children are more free and open in conveying all their problems.

4. Mutual respect among family members

A harmonious family is a family that provides a place for each family member to appreciate the changes that occur and teaches the skills to interact as early as possible with children with a wider environment. Sedangkan menurut Harlock, (2002), faktor yang mempebgaruhi keharmonisan keluarga adalah komunikasi interpersonal, tingkat ekonomi keluarga, sikap orang tua, dan ukuran keluarga. Menurut Sarwono, (dalam Maniriyanto, 2014), keluarga harmonis atau keluarga bahagia adalah apabila dalam kehidupannya telah memperlihatkan factor kesejahteraan jiwa, kesejahteraan fisik, perimbangan antara pengeluaran dan pendapatan keluarga.

5. The quality and quantity of conflict is minimal

Another factor that is no less important in creating family harmony is the quality and quantity of conflict that is minimal if, in a family of frequent disputes and quarrels, the atmosphere in the family is no longer pleasant. In a harmonious family, each family member tries to solve the problem with a cool head and seek the best solution for each problem.

6. There is a close relationship or bond between family members

A close relationship between family members also determines the harmony of a family. A close relationship between family members can be realized by being together, good communication between family members and mutual respect.

D. Relationship of Family Harmony with Delinquency in Adolescents

Many studies conducted by experts find that adolescents who come from caring, warm, and harmonious families can adapt and socialize well with the surrounding environment and adolescents who have a good adjustment in school, usually have a family background harmonious, (Santrock, 2007).

This is in line with the results of Hasanah's research, (2015), which states that there is a very close relationship between family harmony with delinquency in adolescents. Furthermore, the results of the study (Basri in Syarifah Irmawati, 2008) also stated that everyone is obliged to always create and maintain good and effective relationships between parents and children to support the creation of harmonious family life.

Hypothesis: There is a negative relationship between family harmony with delinquency in adolescents.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative approach to the quantitative correlational type of research. The population used was 234, namely all adolescents of SMAN 1 Built with a large sample size of 25% of the total population, which is $25\% \times 234 = 59$ adolescents taken by simple random sampling technique.

Data collection in this study uses two scales namely family harmony scale which is made based on the aspects proposed by Hawari (in Hasanah, 2015) including creating religious life in the family, having time in the family, having good communication between family members, mutual respect among family members, the quality and quantity of conflict that is minimal, the existence of close relationships or ties between family members, and the scale of adolescent acquaintance made based on the aspects raised by Sarwono (2016) including behavior that causes physical harm to others, behavior which causes material casualties, social behavior that does not cause casualties on the side of others, behavior that is against status. Both scales were arranged using the Likert method with a moving score from 1 to 4.

Analysis of the data used to see the relationship of family harmony with acquaintances in adolescents is to use the Pearson Product Moment correlation. The calculation method is assisted by using the SPSS 17.0 for Windows program.

IV. RESULT

1. Assumption Test

The distribution normality test was analyzed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample. As a criterion, if $p > 0.05$ then the distribution is said to be normal, conversely if $p < 0.05$ the distribution is declared abnormal. The results of the normality test of the scale of the relationship of family harmony with juvenile delinquency can be seen in the following table.

TABLE I. Normality Test Calculation Results

Variable	Value Z	Value P	Explanation
1. Family Harmony	1,304	0,067	Normal
2. Juvenile Delinquency	1,442	0,71	Normal

Explanations

Z: Coefecience *Kolmogrov-Smirnov* Z

P: Odds of Occurrence of Errors

Based on the linearity test, it can be seen that the family harmony variable has a linear relationship to the juvenile delinquency variable. As a criterion, if p is different < 0.05 then it is stated to have a linear relationship.

TABLE II. Linearity Calculation Calculation Results

Correational	F	P	Explanation
X-Y	9,237	0,004	Linier

Explanations:

X = Family harmony

Y = Juvenile Delinquency

F = Coefecience Linierarity

P = (Probability)

2. Calculation Results of Person Product Moment Data Analysis Based on the results of the analysis with the Person Product Moment correlation analysis method, it is known that there is a significant negative relationship between family harmony with juvenile delinquency in students of SMAN 1 Terangan, where 0.002 ; $p < 0.05$. This means that the higher the harmony of the family, the lower the level of delinquency in adolescents. Or conversely, the lower the harmony of the family, the higher the level of delinquency in adolescents. Thus, the hypothesis proposed in this study was accepted. In this case, family harmony influences juvenile delinquency of 15.1% and 84.9% of other factors which in this study were not examined.

TABLE III. Pearson Product Moment Data Analysis Calculation Results

Statistik	Koefisien (r_{xy})	Koef.Det. (r^2)	P	BE %	Keterangan
X-Y	-0,389	0,151	0,002	15,1%	Signifikan

Explanation:

X = Family Harmony

Y = Juvenile Delinquency

r_{yx} = Relation Coefecience between X and Y

r^2 = Relation Coefecience between X to Y

p = Chance of Error

BE % = Weight of effective donations X to Y in percent
Ket = Significant at the level of significance $p < 0,010$

2. Results of Calculation of Hypothetical Mean and Empirical Mean

a. Hypothetical Mean

For the family harmony variable, the number of valid items is 26 formatted with a Likert scale in 4 answer choices, then the hypothetical mean $\{(29 \times 5)\} : 2 = 72.5$. Then for juvenile delinquency variables, the number of valid items is 29 items formatted with a Likert scale in 4 answer choices, then the hypothetical mean is $\{(26 \times 5)\} : 2 = 65$

b. Empirical Mean

Based on data analysis, as seen from the distribution normality test analysis it is known that the empirical mean of family harmony variables is 55.22 while for juvenile delinquency variables, the empirical mean is 78.25

c. Criteria

To find out the criteria of family harmony and juvenile delinquency, it is necessary to compare the empirical mean and the hypothetical mean by taking into account the size of the standard deviation of each variable. For the family harmony variable, the SB value is 8.334, while for the juvenile delinquency variable, the SB value is 10.00,00.

From the amount of SB numbers, then for the family harmony variable, if the hypothetical mean $<$ empirical mean, where the difference exceeds one SB, then it is stated that family harmony is high and if the hypothetical mean $>$ empirical mean, where the difference exceeds the SB number, then stated that family harmony is low. Furthermore, for juvenile delinquency variables, if the hypothetical mean $<$ empirical mean, where the difference exceeds one SB, then it is stated that juvenile delinquency is high and if the hypothetical mean $>$ empirical mean, where the difference exceeds one SB, the juvenile delinquency is stated to below.

TABLE IV. Results of Calculation of Hypothetical Average Values and Empirical Average Values

No	Variable	Mean		SD (Deviation Standard)	Explanation
		Hipotetic	Empiric		
1	Family Harmony	72,5	55,2	8,374	Low
2	Juvenile Delinquency	65	78,25	10,004	High

V. DISCUSSION

Based on the calculation results of Pearson Product Moment correlation analysis shows that there is a significant negative relationship between family harmony with juvenile delinquency in students of SMAN 1 Terangan. Looking at the correlation coefficient where $r_{xy} = -0,389$; $p = 0.002 < 0.050$. Based on these results, the hypothesis of this study was accepted. In this study, it is known that family harmony has an effect of 15.1% with 84.9% again influenced by other factors not examined in this study. From the results of this study it is also known that the difference in empirical mean (55.22) with the hypothetical mean (72.5) is categorized as low, and the difference in empirical mean (78.25) with the hypothetical

mean (65) of juvenile delinquency in the high category means lower family harmony, the higher the level of delinquency in adolescents.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Hasanah (2015), which states that there is a very significant relationship between family harmony with delinquency in adolescents, the lower the harmony of the family, the higher the level of delinquency in adolescents.

Furthermore, the results of the study (Basri in Syarifah Irmawati, 2008) also stated that everyone is obliged to always create and maintain good and effective relationships between parents and children to support the creation of harmonious family life. A child who is raised in a broken family will have a greater risk of having an antisocial personality that is prone to juvenile delinquency than a child raised in a harmonious family.

As Santrock (2007) explains, adolescents who come from harmonious families have the ability to adapt and socialize well with the surrounding environment and adolescents who have good adaptations at school, usually have a harmonious family background, and the majority adolescents who are involved in delinquency or committing acts of violence usually come from broken families, families that are not harmonious where fights between fathers and mothers become a daily meal for adolescents, and encourage adolescents to commit violence and misbehavior.

The results of this study are consistent with the phenomena in the previous field, wherein this study it was found that family harmony had an effect of 15.1% while the aspects that influenced family harmony according to Hawari (in Hasanah, 2015) were creating religious life in the family, having family time, good communication between family members, mutual respect between family members, minimal quality and quantity of conflict, the presence of close relationships or ties between family members. Based on data obtained in the research aspect of communication looks low, most teenagers in high school have families that are less attentive and busy with their respective affairs so there is no communication between families and often conflict between families and do not have a close relationship between mother and father, or between parents and children so that most children vent their emotions by acting naughty.

As for other factors that are equal to 84.9% of juvenile delinquency is influenced by factors such as negative identity, low self-control, economic status, environment and others. As explained by Jamaludin (2016) that the factors that influence juvenile delinquency include: the First identity, adolescence is at the stage when the identity crisis is an identity that must be overcome. The second self-control is delinquency which can also be described as a failure to develop sufficient self-control in terms of behaviour. The third family process, namely parental supervision of adolescents, plays an important role in determining whether adolescents will commit delinquency or not. The fourth social class or community, even though now juvenile delinquency is no longer limited to a class of social problems that are lower than in the past, some cultural features of the lower social class tend to trigger delinquency (Jenkins & Bell in Santrock, 2003).

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